

Bakanae and foot rot disease incidence in Basmati 385 nursery in Punjab, Pakistan

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Bakanae and foot rot disease has become a serious disease of Basmati varieties, particularly Basmati 385, in Punjab, Pakistan. The disease can attack the rice plant from preemergence to flowering.

Disease incidence data have been recorded only from the transplanted crop in Pakistan. We conducted a survey to determine the bakanae and foot rot disease incidence in nurseries in traditional rice-growing areas of Sheikhpura, Gujranwala, and Sialkot districts during 1992.

Disease symptoms observed in the nurseries were discolored (whitish) seedlings, which were prevalent in nurseries up to 15-18 d after seeding, and elongated (thin and pale) seedlings, which were found at later stages. The data were recorded in a nursery from four randomly selected spots of 0.09 m² each. Seed source, seed treatment, and water source were also recorded.

Bakanae and foot rot disease incidence on Basmati 385 in the traditional rice-growing areas of Punjab, India. 1992.

Item	Sheikhpura	Gujranwala	Sialkot	Total
Nurseries checked (no.)	89	36	55	180
Diseased nurseries (%)	92.0	97.2	98.1	93.9
Treated seed nursery (%)	3.4	5.5	9.1	5.5
Untreated seed nursery (%)	96.6	94.5	90.9	94.5
<i>Seed source (%)</i>				
Farmers' own	89.8	86.1	94.5	90.5
Punjab Seed Corporation	5.6	-	1.9	3.3
Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku	2.2	2.8	1.9	2.2
Others	2.2	11.1	1.9	3.9
<i>Disease incidence (%)</i>				
Untreated seed				
0-12 d	10.5	6.5	5.6	-
13-24 d	5.4	3.6	3.8	-
25 d and more	1.2	1.7	2.5	-
Av	7.2	3.6	4.5	-
Treated seed	3.3	2.4	2.7	-
Reduction in disease incidence (%)	54.9	33.5	40.7	-

Seeds of 94.5% of the 180 nurseries surveyed were not treated with fungicide. Farmers used their own seed, produced from the previous year's crop, in most (90.5%) of the nurseries (see table). The high number of diseased nurseries (93.9%) might be due to infected seed, indicating the disease's seedborne nature.

Disease incidence was greater in younger nurseries and decreased with age. The highest average incidence (7.2%) was observed in Sheikhpura. Treating seed with a fungicide reduced the incidence 33.5-54.9%. ■

Using gypsum to manage sheath rot in rice

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Foliar application of salts (calcium sulfate, magnesium sulfate, and ammonium molybdate) reduced sheath rot (ShR) incidence, caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Grams and Hawksw, in an earlier greenhouse experiment. We conducted field trials to compare these treatments with soil application of calcium sulfate as gypsum during 1991-92 wet season (WS) (Sep-Feb) in two locations using variety Co 43. Plot size was 5 x 4 m²; treatments were laid out in a randomized block design. Gypsum, at 500 kg/ha, was applied basally and as a topdressing, singly and in combination. Salts and a fungicide, carbendazim, were

Effect of various salts on rice ShR incidence and grain yield.^a Aduthurai, India, 1991-92 WS.

Treatment	Time of application	Mean ShR incidence (%)		Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	50% basal + 50% at 35 d after transplanting (DAT)	21.8 ab	22.8 a	3.6 a	4.0 a
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	50% at 20 DAT + 50% at 35 DAT	20.1 a	21.9 a	3.6 ab	3.6 ab
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	Basal only	-	27.7 ab	-	3.4 ab
Gypsum 500 kg/ha	Topdress only at 25 DAT	-	30.6 b	-	3.7 c
Calcium sulfate 0.2%	Booting and 10 d later	26.5 abc	-	3.2 bcd	-
Magnesium sulfate 0.2%	Booting and 10 d later	28.1 bc	-	3.3 bcd	-
Ammonium molybdate 0.005%	Booting and 10 d later	26.3 abc	-	3.4 abc	-
Carbendazim 0.1%	Booting and 10 d later	20.7 ab	23.0 ab	3.4 ab	3.9 a
Untreated check		31.2 c	40.9 c	3.1 d	2.6 d

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

applied as a foliar application at booting and 10 d later. We measured ShR incidence as a percentage of tillers affected on 25 randomly selected hills/plot, 20 d after the last spray.

In the first trial, applying gypsum to the soil in two equal splits at different

times was comparable with carbendazim in reducing ShR and increasing grain yield significantly (see table). Foliar application of the salts was inferior to the gypsum application.

In the second trial, all gypsum treatments significantly reduced ShR, al-

though only basal applications increased the yield considerably.

Gypsum is a promising treatment for reducing ShR incidence in rice and for increasing grain yield when applied as two equal splits. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Effects of botanical treatments on brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål)

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We tested several extracts from plant species for use in controlling brown planthopper (BPH).

Field-collected BPH populations were cultured in screenhouse insect cages. Sap was extracted from test botanicals using a mortar and pestle and then mixed with water (1:1). Three-week-old TN1 seedlings/pot (7.6-cm-diam) were kept in a screened enclosure. Leaves were pruned at 30 cm above soil level.

Each extract (4 ml/pot) was applied to rice seedlings using a hand sprayer.

Immediately after treatment, about 900 nymphs (4th-5th stages) and adults (3:1) were released and prorated in the enclosure. We counted BPH on the plants after 12 h.

The free-choice experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design replanted twice for each treatment, and replicated five times. Endosulfan-treated and untreated rice plants served as controls.

Some of the botanical treatments were significantly more effective than others, but none were nearly as effective as endosulfan (see table). Untreated plants had the most insects (8.6/plant). Nymphs and adults responded in the same way to treatments. *Azadirachta indica*, *Anonas reticulata*, and *Tinosphora rumphii* appear to have repellent effects on BPH. ■

Effects of botanical treatments on BPH.

Plant species/ chemical	Plant part used	BPH/ plant ^a (no.)
Endosulfan ^b	-	0.5 a
<i>Anonas reticulata</i>	Leaf	3.6 b
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Leaf	4.0 bc
<i>Tinosphora rumphii</i>	Vine	4.6 bcd
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	Fruit rind	6.0 bcde
<i>Pithosporum resiniferum</i>	Leaf	6.3 bcde
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Leaf	6.5 bcde
<i>Dieffenbachia picta</i>	Leaf, stalk	6.5 bcde
<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Leaf, stem	6.5 bcde
<i>Anonas muricata</i>	Leaf	6.8 bcde
<i>Curcuma zedoaria</i>	Rhizome	7.1 bcde
<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Leaf	7.6 de
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Leaf	7.8 de
<i>Anonas squamosa</i>	Leaf	8.1 de
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Leaf	8.6 e
<i>Musa sapientum</i>	Stalk	8.6 e
Control	-	8.6 e

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bThree tablespoons/16 liters of water.

Research methodology

Illustrating the recommendation domain concept in integrated pest management: an Indian case study

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Integrated pest management (IPM) strategies are site-dependent. Among the many reasons for this is that the particular combination of pests and diseases (the injury profile) that affects a given crop is, to a significant extent, driven by location-specific crop management practices. Another reason is that the amount of yield reduction (damage) that can be attributed to a given injury profile depends on the (attainable) yield the crop would have achieved had these pests been absent. The attainable yield reflects a given production situation and is site-

dependent. It is therefore necessary to identify the domains where rice pests and diseases may become constraints to productivity and where differing IPM strategies are to be considered.

Surveys have been jointly initiated by NDUAT, IRRI, and ORSTOM since 1991 to characterize the injury profile associated with differing production situations in Uttar Pradesh, India. The surveys address monsoon season crops in three typical rainfed landforms of two villages. The procedure to analyze this information is exemplified using 1992 data, represent-